

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

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Duration: 40 months

Report on **Milestone 6**

SSHOC web platform continuous marketplace integration with SSHOC service offer 2/3

Dissemination Level	PU
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Actual Achievement Date	30/04/2021
Lead Beneficiary/LTP	10. Trust-IT
Work Package	WP2 Communication, Dissemination and Impact
Task	T2.3 SSHOC web presence
Version	V1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.15

Abstract:

On 30 April 2021, the SSHOC website third iteration went live sshopencloud.eu, and milestone 6 achieved. This fourth release of the SSHOC website aims to raise awareness on the full range of SSHOC tools and services accessible and usable from the SSH Open Marketplace by April 2022. This implementation is focused on an update on the SSHOC results, improved access to SSHOC resources and visibility for the SSHOC user communities.

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1. Introduction

As defined in the SSHOC workplan, task 2.3 SSHOC web presence covers all activities related to the design, development, roll-out and continuous update of the SSHOC web platform. Evolving the SSHOC web platform ensures a service-oriented approach to the SSHOC marketplace developed in WP7, acting as the main project entry point with a multi-view of the SSH landscape, according to the main research lines of the ERICs involved, namely Art and Humanities, Social Science, Linguistics.

The SSHOC web platform is conceived and structured to ensure visibility and easy access to the technologies and services resulting from WP3, as well as innovations mechanisms in data production (WP4), use cases (WP5) and training materials (WP6), targeting data producers and data re-users in the SSH disciplines, as well as industry players.

The web platform will also serve as the main repository for all published content and allow access to project deliverables and external resources. In terms of features, its design allows specific sections dedicated to events and workshops; sections to collect user feedbacks and online surveys, and optionally host any software repository developed within SSHOC, with direct access points to the ERICs websites and other relevant websites, existing catalogues and virtual labs. This task also provides branding for the Marketplace (WP7) and support to improve its Graphical User Interface (GUI) and end-user friendliness. Specific branding of the new services can also be provided, making their look & feel homogeneous under the SSHOC umbrella.

In M28, April 2021, the fourth iteration of the SSHOC web platform was achieved (Milestone 6), this document outlines the milestone, its role and the means of verification to its achievement.

2. Description of the Milestone

Via the achievement of Milestone 6, SSHOC prioritises the web platform as a showcase of the continuous marketplace integration with the SSHOC service offer, where direct access to SSHOC tools and services is ensured and available at month 24. An evolved SSHOC web platform ensures a service-oriented approach to the SSHOC marketplace developed in WP7, acting as the main project entry point providing a multi-view of the SSH landscape, according to the main research lines of the ERICs involved, namely Art and Humanities, Social Science, Linguistics.

2.1. Marketplace and Website distinction and alignment

The SSHOC Marketplace provides contextualisation, offers solutions, list of services/tools that can help users answer their research question. The Marketplace centralises and displays all the tools/services/training materials etc. created and collected under SSHOC WPs.

SSHOC website will ensure the visibility of the WP efforts. Explain the services/tools and results created under all WPs and highlight their availability under SSHOC Marketplace.

Marketplace page with catalogue of services and tools is to be developed within SSHOC. The catalogue uses the same categorisation as the EOSC Portal, services and tools will be described and linked as they appear.

FIGURE 1: EOSC PORTAL CATEGORISATION OF TOOLS AND SERVICES

2.2. Methodology

Work Package 2 has formed a web task force of project members connected to coordination, marketplace, technologies, training and dissemination. This team was tasked to:

- Liaise with ALL WPs.
- Create overview & timeline SSHOC results and services.
- Align categorisation.
- Define technical and content improvement on the website.
- Edit existing and new web content.

A spreadsheet on the Project Shared Google drive internal document repository¹ was created to map all SSHOC Services and Tools pulled out over the 40 months of the project, according to their category, type and planning. The spreadsheet gathers all the information defined in the GA, partners were asked to categorise each of these services and tools according to the categories used in the EOSC portal, to map² the type of each service and tool, updated the delivery dates according to the current planning and refine the description of each service and tool.

¹ SSHOC Consortium internal project document repository in Shared Drive - link to the spreadsheet: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1vZPXOIKbFDyCA1GsUUfavdU00_8rs4wsWzoklXliXyQ/edit#gid=1398076874 [04.03.2020]; access to the repository is restricted to SSHOC Consortium partners; After project finalization, repository will be archived by the project coordinator.

² Blueprint; Commercial solution; Data set / data pool; Demonstrator; Feasibility study; Framework (e.g. software environment, policy document, legal framework); Hardware (e.g. chip, appliance, drone, sensor, system); Infrastructure (e.g. IT infrastructure, transport infrastructure, energy infrastructure, water infrastructure, building etc.); Methodology; Model (e.g. risk model, mathematical model, data model, physical model, business model etc.); Patent (e.g. utility, design patents and plant patents); Policy report; Prototype; Proxy/broker service; Research and/or virtual environment; Scientific publication (Refereed); Scientific publication (Non-refereed); Software (e.g. routine, integrated platform, library, plugins); Standard (e.g. norms, policies); Taxonomy / Ontology; Tool / Toolkit / toolbox; Training (e.g. learning tools, services, modules); White paper or similar publication; Other – please define

On the basis of this mapping, the catalogue was rolled out with the SSHOC branding, timeline and the descriptions of services and tools were edited by the editors in the SSHOC Web Task Force.

2.3. Enhancements to SSHOC Website

On 30 April 2021 the SSHOC web platform was updated to reach its 4th iteration, with the main aim of raising awareness on the full range of SSHOC tools and services accessible and usable from the SSH Open Marketplace by April 2022, and connecting to user communities. This implementation is focused on an update of the SSHOC results, improved access to SSHOC resources and visibility for the SSHOC user communities through the following upgrades:

1. Connection to the Beta release of the SSH Open Marketplace.
2. SSHOC in Action menu item showcasing user communities, stakeholders and user stories.
3. Showcasing Synergies.
4. Update of the SSHOC Services and Tools catalogue.
5. Improving access to the training and training materials.
6. Improving access to the SSHOC resources.
7. Facilitate access to SSHOC internal wiki.

FIGURE 2: WEBSITE STRUCTURE AT START OF MS6 WORKS

FIGURE 3: PLANNED STRUCTURE FOR MS6 AND FUTURE UPDATES: ORANGE INDICATES CHANGES AND NEW ELEMENTS IN THE SITEMAP, LEMON INDICATED CHANGES TO EXISTING PAGES, DARK BLUE MEANS INACTIVE PAGES, WHITE MEANS EXISTING AND UNCHANGED PAGES.

2.3.1. Provide access to the SSH Open Marketplace Beta Release

The SSHOC project web platform facilitates direct access to the Beta Release of the SSH Open Marketplace via a dedicated menu item, via a tailored homepage button and a dedicated banner.

FIGURE 4: SAMPLE OF THE DEDICATED MENU ITEM AND HOMEPAGE BANNER FACILITATING DIRECT ACCES TO THE BETA RELEASE OF THE SSH OPEN MARKETPLACE

FIGURE 5: SAMPLE OF THE HOMEPAGE DEDICATED AREA OF THE SSH OPENMAKETPLACE, TAKING VISITORS DIRECTLY TO ITS BETA RELEASE

2.3.2. SSHOC in Action menu item

As one of the major upgrades, the “SSHOC in Action” menu item is now available on the SSHOC website. This menu item is set in place to showcase the project’s user communities and stories to inspire further connecting with users and uptake of the SSHOC tools and services being developed in the project.

FIGURE 6: OVERVIEW PAGE SSHOC IN ACTION, LINKING TO THE RESEARCH AREAS OF THE SSH.

The SSHOC in Action menu and underlying pages aim at improving visibility of:

- SSHOC Data communities in WP9.
- SSH Open Marketplace Testers.
- SSH Training Community.
- SSHOC Trusted Repositories.
- Use Cases.

- Q&A with users.

2.3.3. Showcasing Synergies

In the first 2 years, SSHOC has already built many valuable synergies with other projects and initiatives, as described in D2.2³. These synergies are built to align on ongoing work, share knowledge and connect with new communities. In the synergies are presented per project or project group.

FIGURE 7: SAMPLE OF THE SSHOPENCLOUD.EU SYNERGIES PAGE.

2.3.4. Update of the SSHOC Services and Tools catalogue

As one of the major upgrades in MS5, the initial [SSHOC Service Catalogue](#) has been updated with new information, updated naming and linking of resources such as deliverables, milestones, news and event

³ D2.2 Preliminary report on user community engagement <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4655993>

items to raise awareness on all project outputs delivered for the tools and services and foster further uptake. In addition, a space in each catalogue item has been set in place to link the DOI of the factsheets as foreseen in WP6 and D2.2.

Survey specific parallel corpora. Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires.
[Home](#) / [Survey specific parallel corpora. Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires.](#)

A database of survey questionnaires' texts.

The first version is compiled from questionnaires from the of European Social Survey (ESS) and the European Values Study (EVS) in the English source language and their translations into Catalan, Czech, French, German, Norwegian, Portuguese, Spanish and Russian.

The second version is compiled from questionnaires from the of European Social Survey (ESS), the European Values Study (EVS) and the the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) in the English source language and their translations into Catalan, Czech, French, German, Norwegian, Portuguese, Spanish and Russian.

Property:
 Datasets

Type:
 Dataset

Accessible at:
<https://www.upf.edu/web/mcsq/>

SSHOC Resources:
[D4.3 Survey specific parallel corpora](#)
[D4.4 Guidelines for building survey-specific corpora](#)

SSHOC News:
[Realising EOSC: Virtual Conference with a Difference](#)

SSHOC Events:
[Translation 4.0 - 2021 CDSI WorkshopSSHOC Webinar: The Multilingual Corpus of Survey QuestionnairesLaTeCH-CLfL 2021 - Workshop on Computational Linguistics for Cultural Heritage, Social Sciences, Humanities and Literature](#)

News

[Workshop Notes: SSHOC Dataverse Translation follow-up event](#)

[Workshop Notes: SSHOC Archaeological Case Study - The Roman Theatre in Catania from Survey to Interactive 4D Visualisation](#)
 A dedicated interdisciplinary community within the SSHOC project is working...

[SSHOC Workshop Notes: Providing canonical training materials for secure data facility professionals](#)
 The Social sciences and Humanities provide researcher infrastructure that...

[SSHOC Workshop Notes: Data Citation in Practice](#)
 The findability of data and other resources is crucially dependent on good...

[Implementing EOSC together: read the report of the EOSC Symposium 2021](#)
 The EOSC Symposium 2021 provided a key engagement opportunity for the EOSC...

FIGURE 8: SAMPLE OF A SSHOC CATALOGUE ENTRY, SHOWCASING ONE OF THE TOOLS DEVELOPED IN THE PROJECT, LINKING THE ACTUAL TOOL DESCRIPTION TO RELATED OUTREACH AND TRAINING RESOURCES, AS WELL AS ITS DELIVERABLES.

2.3.5. Improving access to the training and training materials

The SSHOC consortium has created a large amount of training materials from (online) workshop and meetings. Slides have been published on the SSHOC ZENODO community and recordings have been added to dedicated YouTube lists. In MS6 access to these materials has been improved by linking all material to the dedicated item and add the WP6 training categorisation to filter the events published.

FIGURE 9: FILTERS BASED ON THE WP6 TRAINING CATEGORIES, IMPROVING ACCESS TO THE RELATED MATERIAL

FIGURE 10: EVENT ITEM WITH RELATED RESOURCES: SLIDES, VIDEO RECORDINGS AND REPORT BLOG

2.3.6. Improving access to the SSHOC resources

Due to the growing collection of SSHOC resources, the menu item has been expanded with dedicated submenus for posters, deliverables & milestones, white papers, scientific publications, resources created and published for awareness raising events and the communication kit.

FIGURE 11: SAMPLE OF THE DEDICATED WHITE PAPER SECTION

The [deliverables](#) section has also been expanded with the publishable milestone reports, accessible via an easy-to navigate searchable list, filtered and organised by Work Package. The full suite of position papers, reports and other SSHOC documents are collected in the [dedicated Zenodo Community](#), linked above the main menu and also under "Publications".

FIGURE 12: SAMPLE OF SSHOC MILESTONES ADDED TO THE SSHOC SERVICES AND TOOLS CATALOGUE

2.3.7. Facilitate access to SSHOC internal wiki

To facilitate access to the internal project wiki, access was facilitated via the SSHOC website as shown in figure 3 and the screenshot below.

FIGURE 13: SAMPLE OF THE SUBMENU IMPROVING ACCESS TO THE SSHOC PROJECT WIKI.

Finally, all text on the website has been revisited, rethought and rewritten to ensure clarity and brevity.

3. Role of the Milestone

SSHOC uses various communication channels leveraging project partner networks to produce a set of tailored communication formats targeting different stakeholder groups. The main channels that will be utilised in SSHOC are visualised in the figure below:

FIGURE 14: ELEMENTS DETERMINING AN EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION STRATEGY.

The SSHOC web platform, sshopencloud.eu, is the unique access point for the SSHOC Marketplace and it showcases the project’s objectives results partners, news, and events.

3.1. Means of verification

On 30 April the SSHOC web platform achieved its 4th iteration, the improvements were visible at the website, showcased with the screenshot images showcased in the section 2.3 of this milestone report.

3.2. Delay in the Milestone delivery

Milestone 6 was not finalised in month 24 (December 2020) because the initial milestone was related to the delivery of Milestone 31 Setting up and populating a new ESS repository, postponed to M31 of the project. An amendment was made to decouple the delivery of Milestone 6 from the ESS survey repository and will be connected when ready. Due to this change, the milestone was delivered in M28 of the project.

4. Conclusions and next steps

The SSHOC website will have different iterations during the project's lifetime aligned with the forthcoming results and defined as Milestones 7. The following conclusions can be drawn from the 6th iteration:

- The tools and services spreadsheet set the basis for the SSHOC catalogue, is regularly updated as a blueprint for the catalogue, while also serving as a basis for the onboarding of services and tools to the EOSC marketplace in close collaboration with the EOSC Enhance project.
- The 6th iteration consolidated easy access to the vast amount of resources and outputs developed over the course of the project and prepared access for the upcoming outputs and connecting them to the tools and services being developed in the SSHOC project.
- The 6th iteration brought the activated user communities to the forefront, this needs to be further expanded in MS 7 with the publication of new content and stories.

Next steps planned for MS7:

- Prepare the website to connect and provide access to the final version of the SSH Market Place.
- Develop and connect the SSH Trainers Directory.
- Provide end-users with access to the ESS survey repository as well as the other ERICS repositories present in the SSHOC project.
- Include the DOIs to the graphically designed factsheets of the SSHOC Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to their catalogue entries.
- At the end of the project the Homepage should provide immediate access to the main KERs, as described in the upcoming Exploitation Plan of SSHOC.